

THE ESSENCE OF THE RIGHT OF PRIVATE OWNERSHIP OF LAND IN THE SYSTEM OF PROPERTY TURNOVER

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13629018>

Abstract. *The right of ownership, being the main property right by its nature, acts as the central institution of civil law. With the involvement of land in civil circulation, the formation of the right of private ownership of land, many questions and problems arise that do not yet have an unambiguous solution in civil law science. Ownership as an economic category receives legal consolidation, expressed in the system of legal norms regulating property relations and forming the institution of property rights. In this case, property acts in an objective sense. And in a subjective sense, property is manifested in the consolidation of legal power for a specific person, i.e. the owner. The basis in the system of property rights is the establishment of the owner's authority, which determines the main content of this institution.*

Keywords: *contents property rights, private property rights to land, right of possession, right of use, right of disposal, legislation on property rights, constitutional foundations of private property rights to land, guarantee of property rights to land.*

The right of ownership, being the main property right by its nature, acts as the central institution of civil law. With the involvement of land in civil circulation, the formation of the right of private ownership of land, many questions and problems arise that do not yet have an unambiguous solution in civil law science. Starting to consider the right of ownership of land, we consider it necessary to first turn to the economic aspects of property relations, since the legal regulation of property cannot be understood without delving into its economic essence.

The only source of all material goods necessary for human existence is the process of social production (with the exception of land and other natural resources given to man by nature itself), in which people enter into relationships with each other to recapture material goods from nature. The essence of these relationships is appropriation, i.e. in relation to material goods as one's own. At the same time, the appropriation of some property by one person inevitably entails the alienation of this property from all other persons, otherwise the appropriation loses all meaning. From this point of view, any property (appropriation) is private, because it formalizes the ownership of specific things by specific persons.

According to Tolstoy Yu.K., property means a relationship between people regarding things. At one pole of this relationship is the owner, who treats the thing as his own, at the other - non-owners, i.e. all third parties who are obliged to refrain from any encroachment on someone else's thing, and therefore, on the will of the owner, which is embodied in this thing. Ownership is also inherent in volitional content, since it is the sovereign will of the owner (possession, use and disposal) that determines the existence of the thing belonging to him.

Property as an economic category receives legal consolidation, expressed in the system of legal norms regulating property relations and forming the institution of property rights. In this case, property acts in an objective sense. And in a subjective sense, property is manifested in the consolidation of legal power for a specific person, i.e. the owner.

According to Article 17 of the Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, individuals may own and lease land plots, and legal entities may own, permanently use and lease land plots in accordance with the law. Legal entities and individuals have the right to privatize, in cases provided for by law, non-agricultural land plots that they own on the basis of permanent use (ownership), lease or lifelong inheritable possession.

And in relation to foreign citizens and legal entities, stateless persons, and enterprises with foreign investment, the law does not allow the right of ownership; they may own land plots only on the basis of lease (Part 3 of Article 17 of the Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan). An exception is made for diplomatic missions and equivalent international organizations accredited in the Republic of Uzbekistan that have land plots on the right of ownership arising from the sale by them, in the manner prescribed by law, of buildings or parts of buildings used for the premises of missions, including the residence of the head of the mission, together with the land plots on which they are located, as well as land plots for the construction of buildings of these missions (Part 2 of Article 18 of the Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan). Thus, land legislation restricts foreign persons from having land plots on the right of private ownership.

Each state determines the possibility of granting land for private ownership to foreigners based on its domestic and foreign policy, territorial size, economic growth and development, social significance of land as public property and other factors. As the analysis of the legislation of small European states shows, the size of the territory is not an argument for restrictions. Thus, the land legislation of Luxembourg and Monaco does not contain any prohibitions on the acquisition of real estate in the country. According to the Land Code of Kazakhstan (Part 3, Article 23), land plots may be in the private ownership of foreigners, stateless persons and foreign legal entities (non-governmental) provided for development or built up with industrial and non-production, including residential, buildings (structures) and their complexes, including lands intended for servicing buildings (structures) in accordance with their purpose. In the Russian Federation, security considerations are sufficient grounds for establishing restrictions, due to which foreign citizens are not allowed to acquire land plots in border areas and in other specially designated areas (clause 3, article 13 of the Land Code of the Russian Federation).

In some cases, restrictions may be expressed in the establishment of certain conditions for the acquisition of property. Thus, according to the Icelandic Act on the Right of Ownership and the Right to Use Real Estate of April 6, 1966, No. 19, an exception may be made for persons who have strong ties to the state, for example, due to marriage to an Icelandic citizen. At the same time, maximum sizes of land plots are established for them depending on the purposes of their acquisition by a foreigner. In Egypt, the maximum size of a land plot acquired by foreigners is set at four hectares, and in Turkey, 30 hectares. In addition, a ban is established on the acquisition of land plots located in close proximity to historical monuments. In a number of European countries such as Andorra, Hungary, Denmark, Iceland, Poland, Malta, Turkey, a permit procedure for acquiring real estate has been established for foreigners. In our opinion, the provision of land to foreigners in private ownership under certain legal conditions and for a specific purpose would increase the inflow of investment capital into the national economy and expand the investment attractiveness of the country, as a result of which a foreign investor will invest in the economy reliably, without any fears, because every foreign investor asks the question of what property right his investment activity will be based on and to what extent his private property, investment in the country is protected. Based on the above, we consider it appropriate to establish the right of private

ownership of land plots to foreigners for the implementation of investment activities on the terms and in the manner prescribed by law and ensuring its rational use and protection as national wealth.

It should be especially noted that the basis of the property rights system is the establishment of the owner's authority, which determines the main content of this institution. It is well known that the content of the right of ownership of land is the owner's authority to own, use and dispose of the land.

Ownership of a land plot is a legally secured opportunity for the owner's economic dominance over the land plot.

Use of a land plot is a legally secured opportunity to extract useful properties from it in the process of personal or productive consumption, as well as growing agricultural products, erecting buildings and structures, etc. The right of use is usually based on the right of ownership. However, the owner of a land plot does not have exclusive freedom in choosing the methods of using this plot, since according to land legislation, land must be used for its intended purpose, which is determined by assignment to the appropriate land category, and also, the use of land must be carried out in ways that do not harm the environment. Disposal of a land plot is a legally secured opportunity to determine the fate of a land plot by performing legal acts: alienation of a land plot into the ownership of other persons (sell, donate, exchange, bequeath, transfer as a contribution to the authorized capital of legal entities), lease, pledge. Unlike other property rights to a land plot (the right of permanent use, lifelong inheritable possession and lease), the distinctive feature of the right of ownership of land is mainly the right of disposal, which is absent in other property rights. After all, the person to whom the land plot is granted for use exercises possession and use, but cannot dispose of it.

In support of this, D. Chiniev believes that the right of ownership as a subjective property right is broader in its content in relation to other property rights, since the owner has the exclusive right of possession, use and disposal of his property at his own discretion and in his own interests. The possession by the owner of this entire arsenal of powers indicates the completeness of the right of ownership, and the allocation of possession, use, or limitation of disposal of - incompleteness.

A classic example of regulating the content of the right of ownership of land is the Civil Code of France, where the right of ownership of land includes the owner's right to what is above and below it (Article 552). The owner can make all kinds of plantings and erect buildings at his own discretion, and can also erect underground structures and dig the earth at his own discretion, extract from underground products that are there, subject to the restrictions arising from the laws concerning public safety. The owner of a land plot has the right, at his own discretion, to perform any actions in relation to it that do not contradict the law, do not violate the rights and legally protected interests of other persons and do not harm the environment. National scientists also note that the right of ownership grants the owner power that exceeds all other rights, to freely and fully own, use and dispose of his property, limiting other persons in actions directed against his interests. This dominion of the owner over his property should not be limited except by legislative acts.

According to Bogolyubov S.A., the owner of a land plot does not have absolute freedom in choosing the methods and directions of using his plot: firstly, the land must be used in accordance with its intended purpose, determined by its belonging to a particular category of land, and permitted use, secondly, the use of land must be carried out in ways that should not harm the environment, including the land as a natural object. In our opinion, this is where the specificity of

private ownership of land is manifested, since land is primarily an object of nature, a national treasure, the state's land policy is aimed at the rational use and preservation of land resources in a suitable condition for the next generation, as a result of which the legislation establishes a special legal regime in relation to land.

Nevertheless, Erofeev B.V. notes that the established environmental requirements and requests, the targeted use of these objects, etc., are not, in fact, restrictions on the right of ownership, but establish more precise boundaries of the content of this right, which in any case cannot be unlimited.

Ownership is the basis of a person's true independence and confidence in the future, when property belongs to its owner, he fights for its safety, its protection and increase, and for this he does everything for the sake of strengthening peace and stability in society and the state. In addition, under certain conditions, ownership creates a specific interest in the effective use of limited economic resources. On the contrary, if the rights to resources are common, then economic interest is lost, responsibility for specific economic objects is personified, which does not guarantee their effective use. The latter depends on how effectively the owner is able to dispose of, manage the property, i.e. to exercise the powers known to us.

Agreeing with the opinion of D.A. Chiniev, we would like to note that private ownership of land stimulates the owner to use his resources in the interests of increasing well-being, since in the absence of private property, efficiency in the process of exploitation weakens. The use of a land plot in production by the owner is carried out through rational management. After all, in the absence of a careful attitude to the land (which is expressed in compliance with various measures aimed at improving the quality of the land), its use for its intended purpose with maximum efficiency is impossible. The tenant or user, when using a land plot on a property right, for the sake of profit growth will use the land to the maximum, even violating the rules of use, since he temporarily owns it, various incentives and punishments will not be effective.

However, the stimulating value of private property is lost when it is not properly protected by the state, because without establishing a specific mechanism, guarantees for implementation and protection, the existence of this right does not make sense.

In our country, for many years, the establishment of exclusive state ownership of land and the exclusion of land as an object in property turnover have led to a completely unformed layer of real land owners. As a result of the depreciation of land as a real commodity, an increase in the number of illegal actions in relation to land by officials led to the failure to form a class of owners and the creation of serious obstacles to attracting foreign investors to the economy of the republic, which in turn has a negative impact on the investment attractiveness of the country.

It should be especially noted that the consolidation of private ownership of land in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the new edition was one of the main reforms implemented in our country in recent years and is of great political importance. Today, the policy pursued in our country to liberalize the economy, introduce real market principles into it and embody the idea of private ownership of land in the constitution creates a certain harmony with the reforms being carried out.

It is necessary to note the fact that in recent years the issue of introduction of private property rights to land has been increasingly discussed in scientific publications and forums. Analysis of scientific and legal literature allows us to make certain statements regarding the

consolidation of private property rights to land. What does the introduction of private property rights to land lead to and what impact does it have from a legal and economic point of view?

Firstly, the right of private property rights to land gives the owner the right of possession, use and, most especially, disposal at his own discretion and in his own interests in full. Thus, previously the owner, as the holder of property rights to land, could not fully have full powers in relation to the land, could not fully dispose of the land plot itself, since he had only property rights to them. This, in turn, infringed on the owner's ability to protect his rights in relation to the land. Secondly, the establishment of private ownership of land makes it possible to include it in full civil circulation, and this in turn makes the land an object of various civil transactions of purchase and sale, exchange, donation, inheritance, pledge. Previously, the owner could not leave the land itself as an inheritance, but only certain rights to it. Inclusion of a land plot as an object of collateral helps to increase the creditworthiness of individuals, because land as real estate is a reliable subject of surety. The introduction of land into civil circulation leads to the use of appropriate market mechanisms. Thirdly, land is not only a natural resource, but also the main economic resource of the country, since it forms the basis of the economy, agriculture in general. The establishment of private ownership of land contributes to investment attractiveness and improvement of the investment climate in the country. After all, every foreign investor is interested in confident investment without barriers and full protection of his rights by the laws of the invested state.

Fourthly, if the land is privately owned, the procedure for its seizure for public needs will be different from the owner of property rights to the land: no one can take away the land without the consent of the owner. It can be said that the owner has protection from demolition. Fifthly, the possibilities for the effective use of land resources are expanded. Each land owner cares about the proper protection and improvement of the condition of the land plot. After all, the main factor in increasing the efficiency of land use are the incentives created by private property rights. Without being the owner of the land, a person does not feel like a real owner without the motivation to preserve and improve the land, which hinders the high efficiency of his labor.

Sixthly, the introduction of private property in land leads to the formation of financial resources of the country, since with the help of privatization of land plots an additional source of income is created in the state budget.

However, along with the positive aspects of this important innovation, there are also a number of negative consequences that occur in the socio-economic spheres.

An analysis of the experience of various countries shows the presence of the following factors after the introduction of private property in land:

a) the danger of the formation of large "latifundia" of the Latin American type as agricultural land with hired workers. Historically, in Latin America, latifundia were donated by colonial authorities, in Europe feudal lands arose as a gift from the king to a nobleman. To prevent these lands, it is possible to apply the practice used in foreign countries. For example, in Denmark, New Zealand, restrictions are established on the size of land plots purchased by one family;

b) transformation of banks into large landowners when the mortgaged land plot is transferred to the hands of the mortgagee-bank. Here it is possible to limit the acquisition of land by banks by legislatively fixing the bank's obligation to sell the debtors' land plots within a certain period of time (in the USA within two years) and others. It should also be noted that the presence of two different legal regimes for two inextricably linked things, which are the building and the land plots. In this aspect, an important issue is also the fixing of the principle of the unity of the

fate of the land plot and the objects firmly connected with it, according to which all objects firmly connected with the land plots follow the fate of the land plots, with the exception of cases established by law. Alienation of a land plot without a building or structure located on it, if they are owned by one person, is not permitted; in this case, a transaction for the alienation of buildings and structures located on a land plot, carried out separately from the land plot, must be recognized as invalid; the impossibility of separate alienation of a land plot and the real estate located on it also applies to the termination of rights to land plots in the event of requisition, confiscation of a building, foreclosure on the said property for the owner's obligations.

We can emphasize that one of the most important reforms implemented in our country in recent years is the recognition of land as private property. It can be emphasized that the basis of such a great political will of the state is the development of land ownership relations, granting owners such rights as sale, donation, exchange, pledge, bequest of privatized land to other persons, and guaranteeing these rights from the point of view of the law.

Recognition of land as private property from an economic point of view, in turn, leads to the expansion of a new generation of owners in Uzbekistan, the development of the land market, and increased efficiency of land use. At the same time, the introduction of market mechanisms in the process of land use, ensuring the stability of property and legal relations in this direction and guaranteeing the property rights of landowners, will become the legal basis for the further functioning of market mechanisms in the field of land use in the country. Because one of the main goals of the state is to give a broad path to entrepreneurship and protect the rights of private property owners in the context of developing market relations. Thanks to these changes, Article 68 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan guarantees the introduction of market mechanisms in the sphere of land use in our country, ensuring the stability of property and legal relations in this sphere, and guaranteeing the property rights of land owners. The implementation of this norm in the future will allow owners, in particular citizens and business entities, to secure their property rights to land at the constitutional level. This, in turn, serves as reliable protection and guarantees of the rights of owners, and also strengthens their obligation to take good care of the land.

Transferring land to private ownership gives us, first of all, the right to use, own and, most importantly, dispose of the land plot and all buildings and structures located on it for our own benefit. Land is an important economic resource. Firstly, it is a natural resource, and secondly, it is an economic resource. Land is also an extremely reliable object of collateral. If the land is not privately owned, it will not be possible to include it in full civil circulation. It will be impossible to conclude a purchase and sale agreement with it, it is not subject to collateral. Now, if the regime of full private ownership is applied to land, it can be sold, mortgaged and left on the basis of full inheritance of civil legal relations associated with this land.

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